

**Значение железнодорожного транспорта для национальной и
международной экономики**

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Аннотация. В статье рассматривается значение железнодорожного транспорта для национальной и международной экономики. Выделены его роль в обеспечении территориального экономического развития, расширении внешнеэкономических связей и повышении эффективности логистики. Рассмотрены преимущества железнодорожных перевозок по сравнению с другими видами транспорта, в том числе большая вместимость, скорость и экономичность при перевозке грузов на дальние расстояния. Подчёркивается необходимость учёта капитальных затрат и планирования инфраструктуры при развитии железнодорожной сети.

Ключевые слова: железнодорожный транспорт, экономика, логистика, грузоперевозки, инфраструктура, эффективность.

**The Importance of Railway Transport for the National and International
Economy**

Annotation. The article discusses the importance of railway transport for national and international economies. It highlights its role in ensuring territorial economic development, expanding foreign economic relations, and improving logistics efficiency. The advantages of railway freight transport over other transport modes are considered, including higher capacity, speed, and cost-effectiveness for long-distance shipments. The necessity of considering capital investments and infrastructure planning in the development of the railway network is emphasized.

Keywords: railway transport, economy, logistics, freight transportation, infrastructure, efficiency.

The transport system enables the formation of the management structure of individual territories and optimizes internal and external economic relations. Transport affects the level of a country's accessibility, determines the territorial organization of production, and contributes to deeper specialization and integrated development. Thus, the development of transport is a necessary condition for territorial economic growth, increasing the efficiency of existing resource utilization by linking the components of

economic activity. The development of the transport network ensures the expansion of foreign economic relations.

Railway transport holds an important place in the economic system. The railway complex includes railway vehicles and the supporting production infrastructure whose activities are based on rail transport. Railways play a defining role within the railway transport complex.

Railway transport is the leading link in the transport system of the CIS countries, including Uzbekistan, and is a system-forming element of the economy that ensures effective socio-economic development while expanding and deepening integration processes. Railway transport meets the needs of citizens, economic entities, and the state for passenger and freight transport in a timely and high-quality manner, creating conditions for its effective operation and industry development, and ensuring the economic integrity of the country.

Railway freight transport has both advantages and disadvantages compared to other modes of transport.

Additionally, the advantages of railway transport include the speed of wagon flow and its versatility as a mode of transport, meaning the ability to handle freight flows of any volume up to 75–80 million tons annually in a given direction, which favorably distinguishes it from other transport types.

The efficiency of railway transport increases when it is necessary to transport large quantities of goods over long distances, especially when delivering from or to hard-to-reach areas.

The projected load on railway lines and access to new markets or resources determine the investment attractiveness of large-scale projects in the development of the railway network.

In organizing the railway system, it is important to consider the possibility of congestion on certain sections of main lines and network fragments at major railway junctions. Congestion most often occurs at railway border crossings.

In the freight transport market, the demand is determined by entities sending and receiving goods, while the supply is provided by railway companies. It is clear that the most elastic part of the demand for railway transport comes from companies not engaged in mineral extraction or raw material delivery, namely small companies for which alternatives to rail transport include road, water, or air transport.

It is worth noting that, according to some authors, the insufficient pace of railway sector development holds back the development of many other sectors. The interconnection of sectoral development is demonstrated in the input-output model of Nobel laureate Wassily Leontief.

Nevertheless, it is necessary to consider the high capital investments required for constructing railway tracks and maintaining them in the required condition. The higher the actual concentration of freight flow, the higher the efficiency and attractiveness of investing in the railway freight transport sector.

Thus, railway transport plays a leading role in the economic development of territories, mainly through its logistical function. Compared to road transport, railway transport is characterized by lower costs and higher capacity. The reduction in the share of transport costs in the cost price leads to increased product competitiveness and enhances the overall utility for end consumers, as it reduces budget constraints.

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